

SHAFTOLINING SHIFOBAXSH XUSUSIYATALARINI TADQIQ ETISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ma'lumki, dunyo miqyosida farmatsevtika sohasida ishlab chiqarilayotgan dori vositalarining deyarli asosiy qismi dorivor o'simliklar xom ashyosidan tayyorlanmoqda. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, dunyo aholisining qariyb 80 foizi dorivor o'tlar asosidagi mahsulotlardan foydalanadi. Mualliflar tomonidan olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqot ham respublikamizda dorivor o'simlik hisoblangan shaftoli daraxtining barglaridan ekstrakt tayyorlashga qaratilgan bo'lib, tadqiqot davomida oddiy shaftolining tarkibida biologic faol moddalar, vitaminlar, minerallar, flavanoidlar va boshqa ko'plab tibbiyot uchun ahamiyatli bo'lgan xususiyatlarini aniqlaganlar. Tadqiqot davomida oddiy shaftoli barglaridagi karotinoidlar o'rtacha miqdori $0,087\% \pm 0,006$ miqdoriy tarkibi aniqlagan bo'lib, ushbu ko'satkichlar oddiy shaftolidan tibbiyotda qo'llash uchun dorivor ekstraktlar tayyorlash imkonini beradi degan xulosani aytish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlari: oddiy shaftoli barglari, karotinoidlar.

Tadqiqot usullari: Tadqiqotda hammasi bo'lib beshta xom ashyo namunasi tahlil qilindi. Karotinoidlarni miqdoriy jihatdan aniqlash spektrofotometrik usul bilan amalga oshirildi ФС.2.5.0106.18 ga ko'ra «Шиповника плоды» usulida amalga oshirildi. Ekstraktidagi karotenoidlarning umumiy miqdorini spektrofotometrik usul bilan aniqlandi.

Olingan natijalar: O'simliklarda yangi sabzavotlar, rezavorlar va mevalarga yorqin sariq, qizil yoki to'q sariq rang beradigan flavanoidlarga kiradi. Bizning tanamizda sodir bo'ladigan metabolik jarayonlar uchun karotenoidlar juda samarali antioksidantlar rolini o'ynaydi. shuningdek A vitamini sintez qilinadigan alfa- va beta-karotinlar: immunitet tizimining muhim elementi, hujayra membranalarining tarkibiy qismidir. Ko'rish va ko'z shox pardasining mustahkamlashda ishtirok etadi. Har qanday karotenoidning asosiy va eng muhim vazifasi hujayralarni antioksidant himoya qilish bilan bog'liq. Har qanday hujayralar bunday himoyaga muhtoj, karotenoidlar miya hujayralari, qon tomirlari, yurak barcha turdagi boshqa organlarga o'zlarining samaradorligini hamma joyda ko'rsatishga intiladi.

Shunga ko'ra shaftoli ham karatinoidlar manbai bo'lib, undan dorivor ekstrakt tayyorlash uchun miqdorini aniqlash lozim bo'ladi. Spektrofotometrik usullar juda oddiy va tezdir. Ularning asosiy afzalliklaridan biri shundaki, xlorofillarning mavjudligi karotenoidlarni aniqlashga xalaqit bermaydi.

Komponentlarning sifat tarkibini ekstraktning yutilish spektrlarini olish va maksimal so'rilish bo'yicha komponentlarni aniqlash orqali baholash mumkin.

Karatinoidlarni miqdoriy baholash natijalari 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

1-jadval

Oddiy shaftoli barglarida β -karotin bo'yicha karotenoidlarning tarkibi

Namuna	Shaftoli barglarida β -karotin bo'yicha karotenoidlarning miqdori
№ 1	0,088 %
№ 2	0,090 %
№ 3	0,085 %
№ 4	0,080 %
№ 5	0,092 %

Olingan natijalarga ko'ra birinchi namunada shaftoli barglarida β -karotin bo'yicha karotenoidlarning 0.088%, ikkinchi namunada esa 0.090%, uchinchi namunamizda

0.085%, keying namunalarimizda esa 0.080-0.092% ni tashkil etgan. Eng ko'p β -karotin bo'yicha karotenoidlarning miqdori beshinchi namunada aniqlandi.

2-jadval

Shaftoli xom ashyosida karotinoidlar miqdorini aniqlashning metrologik tavsifi

D O'M	X o'rt, %	S ²	S	F , %	T (P, f)	Δ X	E , %
Sh aftoli barglari	0, 087	0,0 0002	0,0 0469	9 5	2 ,78	0, 013	1 4,98

2-jadval ma'lumotlaridan ko'rinib turibdiki, karotinoidlar miqdori, β -karotin nuqtai nazaridan, oddiy shaftoli barglarida $0,087\% \pm 0,00$ ni tashkil etdi.

Muhokama: Tadqiqot davomida oddiy shaftoli barglarida karatinoidlar miqdorini aniqlashda oddiy, oson usuldan foydalanilganligi hamda olingan natijani ishonchliligiga alohida e'tiborga sazovordir. Chunki spektrofotometrik usul orqali olingan natija metodologik tavsif orqali matematik xisoblar orqali qayta tahlil qilinmoqda. Bu esa o'tkazilgan tadqiqot olingan natijalari ishonchliligini bildiradi.

Xulosa: Mualliflar tomonida olib borilgan tadqiqot oddiy shaftoli barglaridan dorivor ekstrakt tayyorlashga qaratilgan bo'lib, shaftoli barglarida karatinoidlarni aniqlash ilmiy ishning bir qismi hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot davomida oddiy shaftoli bargidan karatinoidlarni ajratib olishda oddiy va oson usuldan foydalanilganligi tadqiqot yutug'i bo'lib, olingan keratinoid miqdori ham (0.080-0.092%) dorivor ekstrakt tayyorlash uchun yetarli miqdor hisoblanadi.

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